

3D-Printed Porous Hydroxyapatite Formed via Enzymatic Mineralization

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Abstract

Bone is a hierarchically organized, lightweight tissue that combines remarkable mechanical resilience with low density and can be repaired if damaged. This fascinating combination of properties arises from the hierarchical structure of bone and its locally changing composition, enabled by the controlled growth of hydroxyapatite (HA) crystals within a collagen-rich extracellular matrix. Inspired by the excellent density-normalized mechanical properties of bone, a lot of excellent work has been devoted to the fabrication of porous HA-based materials that can be used, for example, as bone graft substitutes. However, their fabrication typically involves high-temperature sintering, which is energy-intensive and restricts the incorporation of biologically active components that are typically thermo-labile. These processing limitations hinder scalability and reduce the potential for integration with living tissue, presenting a critical challenge in the development of clinically relevant bone repair materials. Here, we introduce an enzyme-mediated strategy to 3D print load-bearing porous HA-based composites through an energy-efficient, benign process that is conducted at room temperature. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), an enzyme relevant to bone formation, is embedded in naturally derived hydrogel microfragments and mixed with enzyme-free fragments included to tune the porosity of the final composite. The jammed microfragments are 3D printed in air at room temperature and subsequently mineralized under mild aqueous conditions. The resulting scaffolds exhibit up to 52 vol% porosity, compressive strengths of 3.65 MPa (5.5 MPa·g⁻¹·cm³ specific strength), and low cytotoxicity toward osteoblasts. This sintering-free approach offers control over porosity and mineral distribution and enables the fabrication of biocompatible, low-density mineralized architectures under physiological conditions. We foresee the combination of mechanical performance, bioactivity, and benign, energy-efficient processing to open up new

avenues for bone tissue engineering and mineral repair applications where broken structures have the potential to bear significant loads much faster than currently available solutions do.

Introduction

Bone mineralization is a highly regulated physicochemical and biochemical process involving the nucleation and growth of hydroxyapatite (HA) crystals within a collagen-based extracellular matrix. The resulting tissue exhibits a hierarchical architecture that makes bone lightweight and mechanically robust^[1-3], enabling its function as a key component in load-bearing biological systems that support locomotion.^[4] Motivated by bone's exceptional density-normalized mechanical properties, porous HA-based ceramics have been extensively explored as biomedical scaffolds^[5], in catalysis^[6], and for energy storage.^[7] HA-based materials are particularly attractive for bone repair, as they are chemically similar to native bone and promote tissue integration. While bone has the capacity to regenerate small defects, large injuries often surpass its self-healing ability, particularly in cases of poor vascularization or disease.^[8]

An effective bone substitute must be biocompatible, structurally similar to native bone, and exhibit similar density-normalized mechanical strength.^[9] Autologous bone remains the clinical gold standard for grafting due to its good biological performance, despite the risks and limitations associated with harvesting from a secondary site. Metallic implants offer an alternative for load-bearing applications; however, their high elastic moduli, up to 110 GPa, far exceed those of native bone and may lead to stress shielding and implant-related complications.^[10] In contrast, hydroxyapatite is biocompatible and does not trigger inflammatory responses.^[8] Additionally, the porosity of synthetic HA can be tailored to mimic that of trabecular bone, which can reach up to 65 vol%.^[11]

Synthetic porous HA ceramics are commonly fabricated by infiltrating pre-synthesized commercial HA particles into polymeric sponges, sacrificial templates, or by using porogens. These particles are typically consolidated via sintering at temperatures up to 1300 °C.^[12-19] The processing temperature can be reduced to 120 °C through hydrothermal synthesis of HA particles^[20] or to around 60°C through sol-gel methods.^[21] However, also in these cases, thermal treatments around 500-700°C are needed for consolidation, rendering the processing energy-consuming. Moreover, such high temperature treatments prevent the controlled integration of thermolabile biological components and can negatively affect the bioactivity and biodegradability of the scaffolds.^[22] To mitigate these limitations, methods involving freezing cycles have been developed.^[23-25] Yet, they are also energy-consuming, require longer

fabrication times, and the resulting composites often exhibit inferior density-normalized mechanical properties.

Inspired by the biomineralization processes observed in nature, alkaline phosphatase (ALP) has been employed to induce mineralization under mild conditions within hydrogels^[26,27] and biofilms.^[28] ALP, which can be expressed by bacteria such as *E. coli*^[28], catalyzes the hydrolysis of organic phosphate substrates into inorganic phosphate. This localized increase in phosphate concentration promotes mineral deposition.^[3] Using this strategy, amorphous^[26,29] and crystalline^[27] hydroxyapatite (HA) have been incorporated into bulk hydrogels, enhancing their stiffness by up to three orders of magnitude. However, these materials were exclusively processed via casting methods, which did not offer control over the porosity. ALP has also been incorporated into acrylamide-based inks for 3D printing using Direct Ink Writing (DIW), enabling the fabrication of multilayered structures with relatively simple geometries. Nevertheless, these inks relied on synthetic monomers and inorganic rheological modifiers, yielding dense composites that lack micrometer-scale porosity.^[30]

Here, we present an enzyme-mediated strategy for the fabrication of 3D-printable, porous HA structures, which can be processed at room temperature. This strategy does not require any sintering step, such that it offers a more energy-efficient and rapid alternative to conventional methods used for producing hydroxyapatite-based porous scaffolds. This is achieved by encapsulating ALP within hydrogel microfragments, which are direct ink written into 3D structures and mineralized under mild aqueous conditions to form HA-organic composites. By blending enzyme-containing and enzyme-free microfragments, the porosity and spatial distribution of minerals can be finely tuned, reaching porosities up to 52 vol% and mineral fractions up to 40 vol%. These low-density composites achieve specific compressive strengths of up to 6 MPa·g⁻¹·cm³, aligning with the range reported for human trabecular bone with similar porosity.^[31–33] Their compression moduli can reach up to 40 MPa·g⁻¹·cm³, approaching the lower bound of values observed in various human bone components. Importantly, the fragments are formulated from biocompatible, naturally derived polymers, resulting in HA-mineralized scaffolds that exhibit low cytotoxicity toward osteoblasts, highlighting their potential for tissue engineering applications. The combination of energy-efficient processing, 3D printability, tunable porosity, and bone-comparable density-normalized mechanical properties positions these composites as promising candidates for bone repair applications.

Results and Discussion

To confine mineralization to defined locations and enable room temperature 3D printing, we embed the enzyme alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in soft hydrogel microfragments. To minimize the risk of polymer-induced adverse cell reactions to our material, we employ gelatin as a

model hydrogel. Gelatin is a denatured form of collagen whose composition and structure resemble components of the extracellular matrix. Moreover, it contains RGD motifs, which are critical for promoting cell adhesion.^[34] Gelatin is a solid at room temperature, such that in its unmodified state and without additives, it cannot be processed through extrusion-based approaches such as direct ink writing (DIW) at room temperature. Gelatin can be directly ink written if heated during the printing process.^[38,39] This process, however, requires close temperature control during the printing and hence, dedicated instrumentation. Gelatin can be direct ink written at room temperature if chemically modified to enable photocrosslinking^[36] and optionally combined with nanofillers^[37], or if a sacrificial bath is present.^[38] Unmodified gelatin can be direct ink written at room temperature without the need for any sacrificial bath or rheomodifiers if formulated as jammed spherical microgels.^[40] Spherical particles are typically produced from emulsion drop templates that must be stabilized with surfactants. Surfactants risk compromising the biocompatibility of the final product.^[41,42] To mitigate this risk, we form gelatin microfragments by cryo-milling bulk gelatin. The resulting microfragments are polydisperse and have irregular shapes, as illustrated in **Figure 1a-b**. The average equivalent diameter of enzyme-containing and enzyme-free microfragments is 76 μm , as shown in **Figure S1 a-b**.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the formulation of an ink composed of a mixture of enzyme-containing and enzyme-free fragments. a) Gelatin fragments containing alkaline phosphatase and b) enzyme-free gelatin fragments are produced from bulk hydrogels through cryo-milling. c) The two fragment populations are mixed, suspended in an aqueous solution containing alginate, and jammed. d) The ink is 3D printed at room temperature in air before being soaked into a calcium chloride-containing aqueous solution to crosslink the alginate. The solidified granular material is transferred into a glycerophosphate-containing aqueous solution to initiate the mineralization of the enzyme-containing fragments (e). f) Photograph of

a 3D printed and mineralized hollow cylinder. Scale bar 1 cm. g) Schematic illustration of the ALP-induced mineralization of hydroxyapatite. ALP triggers the hydrolysis of calcium glycerophosphate into PO_4^{3-} and glycerol. PO_4^{3-} reacts with Ca^{2+} to form calcium phosphate.

We expect the mineralization of the scaffold to be restricted to the microfragments containing ALP. Because microfragments are densely packed within the jammed hydrogel rather dense calcium phosphate-based scaffolds should form. To introduce pores into these scaffolds, we mix ALP-containing microfragments with ALP-free ones, as schematically shown in **Figure 1a-c**.

To ensure good shape retention of the granular hydrogel even if subjected to media exchanges during mineralization, we add 4 wt% alginate to the surrounding phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution. The fragments are jammed through centrifugation, 3D printed in air, and exposed to an aqueous solution containing calcium chloride (CaCl_2), which crosslinks alginate^[43] and thereby solidifies the granular structure. The granular scaffold is incubated in an aqueous solution containing 0.1 M calcium glycerophosphate buffered to pH 9.5, as shown in **Figure 1d-e**. The incubating solution is exchanged once per day for 7 days to form self-supporting mineralized structures, as demonstrated by the printed hollow cylinder in **Figure 1f**.

During mineralization, alkaline phosphatase cleaves the phosphate ester bond of calcium glycerophosphate to form phosphate PO_4^{3-} , which reacts with free Ca^{2+} ions present in the surrounding medium to form hydroxyapatite,^[3] as schematically shown in **Figure 1g**. To quantify the mineralization kinetics, we perform thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) as a function of the mineralization time. The mineral content of granular scaffolds exclusively composed of enzyme-containing fragments rapidly increases up to 57 wt% within the 1st day of mineralization. The mineral subsequently grows more slowly, reaching a plateau around 68 wt% after 7 days of incubation, as shown in **Figure 2a**. This two-stage mineralization kinetics is similar to that of human bone, yet human bone forms more slowly; it typically takes several months for bone to fully mineralize.^[44] The final mineral content is more than 40% higher than that reported for ALP-mediated mineralization performed in acrylamide-based hydrogels.^[30]

Calcium phosphate has many different polymorphs whose mechanical properties are distinct.^[45,46] To identify the structure of the formed calcium phosphate, we perform X-ray diffraction (XRD) on samples that have been mineralized for 7 days. This analysis reveals a predominant hydroxyapatite structure, with the main diffraction peaks located at $2\theta = 25.9^\circ$, 32° , 39.7° , 46.8° , 49.5° , 53.5° , and 64° , as shown in **Figure 2b**.^[47,48] The defect density within HA-based ceramics is usually indicated as their calcium/phosphorus atomic ratio (Ca/P). To identify this ratio, we perform Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)-Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS). This analysis reveals a Ca/P ratio of 1.3, as shown in **Figure 2c**. This ratio is below the theoretical value of hydroxyapatite, which is 1.67^[49], indicating that the

formed mineral is Ca^{2+} deprived. This analysis suggests that some Ca^{2+} ions have been replaced by other cations not detected in the EDS analysis or vacancies. Note that hydroxyapatite of natural bones typically also possesses Ca/P ratios below the stoichiometric value.^[50]

A closer inspection of the XRD traces reveals some broad, low-intensity peaks, suggesting the presence of some amorphous phase or nm-size hydroxyapatite crystals; such small crystals are also present in biogenic hydroxyapatite.^[50,51] To better characterize the morphology of the HA crystals, we employ TEM analysis. The minerals contain 10-20 nm long plate-like nanocrystals, as shown in **Figure 2d**. This structure resembles the morphology of HA crystals synthesized using low-temperature hydrothermal methods.^[52,53] In addition, TEM analysis reveals rounded mineral clusters, as shown in **Figure 2e**. Selective area electron diffraction (SAED) is performed to confirm the crystalline structure prevalent within the core of the HA-based composites, as shown in **Figure 2e i-ii**, and the amorphous structure prevalent at their edges, as exemplified in **Figure 2e iii**. The SAED images display concentric diffraction rings, indicative of a polycrystalline structure. The brightest ring in the SAED pattern in **Figure 2e i-ii** corresponds to a spatial frequency of 3.74 nm^{-1} , yielding a calculated interplanar spacing of 2.68 \AA . This value closely matches the (211) reflection of hydroxyapatite, consistent with the strongest peak at 25.9° reported in the XRD spectrum. Additional rings from other SAED zones yield d-spacings of 3.36 \AA , 2.18 \AA , and 1.82 \AA , which are assigned to the (002), (310)/(321), and (213) planes of HA, respectively.^[54] These assignments confirm the successful formation of nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite in our scaffold.

Figure 2. Characterization of HA grown in enzyme-containing fragments. a) Mineral weight fraction as a function of the mineralization time. The filled symbols represent data points of individual measurements, empty symbols the mean values. b) XRD pattern of HA grown for 7 days in enzyme-containing gel fragments. The peaks at $2\theta = 25.9^{\circ}$, 32° , 39.7° , 46.8° , 49.5° , 53.5° , and 64° are characteristic of hydroxyapatite. c) TEM-EDX elemental spectrum showing the peaks at 0.3, 0.5, 2, and 3.6, assigned to C, O, P, Ca of hydroxyapatite, and 8 keV assigned to Cu of the sample holder. d) Overview and e) close-up TEM image of HA crystals with SAED regions and the relative diffraction patterns showing crystalline (i-ii) and amorphous (iii) regions of the minerals.

To test if the porosity of the hydroxyapatite-based composites can be tuned, we mix different weight ratios of ALP-loaded to enzyme-free fragments and add a control solely composed of ALP-containing fragments. A visual inspection of mineralized scaffolds made from samples containing mixtures of ALP-containing and enzyme-free microfragments reveals μm -sized surface pores, as indicated in the photograph in **Figure 3a i-iii**. By contrast, controls have much fewer and smaller pores, as shown in Figure 3a iv. Note that the appearance of control samples locally varies, suggesting that the mineral content is non-uniform, as shown in **Figure 3a iv**.

Figure 3. Morphology of mineralized scaffolds. a) Photographs of mineralized disks obtained from inks made of a mixture of enzyme-containing and enzyme-free fragments with 33 wt% (i, pink), 50 wt% (ii, purple), and 67 wt% (iii, beige) enzyme-containing fragments. The surface of the control made from an ink containing 100 wt% enzyme-containing fragments partially collapses, as indicated by the arrow (iv, blue). The weight ratios are schematically represented as insets. b) μCT scan of the core of HA scaffold made from 100 wt% enzyme-containing fragments surrounded by a dense shell (i, blue) (ii), and samples containing 67 wt% (beige) enzyme-loaded fragments where a hole is also visible in the core (iii) and not in the surface (iv). By contrast, samples made from 50 wt% (v, purple) and 33 wt% (vi, pink) enzyme-loaded fragments are homogeneously mineralized. The red areas and arrows indicate gelatin. c)

Mineral weight fraction of the composite as a function of the wt% of enzyme-containing fragments they have been made from after 1 day (empty squares) and 7 days of mineralization (full squares). The asterisks indicate samples whose mineral content is heterogeneous throughout the volume. d) Pore size distributions showing the Feret diameter of composites made from scaffolds containing 33 wt% (pink) and 50 wt% (purple) enzyme-loaded fragments. For the two distributions, $p < 0.001$.

To visualize the morphology of our scaffolds with a higher spatial resolution, we perform micro-computed tomography (μ CT). The mineral content of controls is significantly higher within an approximately 300 μ m thick surface shell and decreases towards their center of the sample, as shown in **Figure 3b i-ii**. By contrast, samples made from scaffolds containing only 33 wt% enzyme-containing fragments are homogeneously mineralized, as shown in **Figure 3b iii-iv**. Our results suggest that composites made from samples containing no more than 50 wt% ALP-loaded fragments are homogeneously mineralized. We assign this result to a facilitated diffusion of calcium glycerophosphate to the mineralization sites of samples containing significant amounts of pores. Indeed, hydroxyapatite-based composites made from scaffolds with 50 wt% ALP-loaded fragments contain 50 vol% pores, whereas $41 \text{ vol}\% \pm 8\%$ of their volume is occupied by minerals, as shown in **Figure S2**. Remarkably, the pore fraction of samples formed from scaffolds comprising 33 and 50 wt% enzyme-containing fragments is, within experimental error, the same, $38 \text{ vol}\% \pm 7\%$, as shown in **Figure S2**.

To assess the influence of the porosity on the mineralization kinetics, we perform TGA on samples made from varying contents of ALP-containing enzymes after one and seven days of mineralization. The mineral formation in our scaffolds is fast, up to 87 wt% of the minerals form within the first 24 hours of incubation for samples mineralized from 50 wt% ALP-containing fragments, as shown in **Figure 3c**. After 1 day of mineralization, the mineral content of samples made from 33 wt% ALP-containing fragments is 48 wt%, whereas it is 57 wt% for samples entirely made from ALP-containing fragments, as shown in **Figure 3c**. After 7 days of mineralization, the mineral content reaches 59 wt% for samples made from 33 wt% ALP-containing fragments and 68 wt% for controls, as shown in **Figure 3c**. These results suggest that the maximum mineral content is limited by the diffusion of calcium glycerophosphate into the substrate, required to achieve a homogeneous mineralization.

The diffusivity of reagents into the mineralized scaffolds strongly depends on the size and connectivity of the pores. We estimate these parameters from our μ CT scans. The pores are polydisperse, and their morphologies ill-defined. To compare results between the different samples, we quantify the Feret diameter, which is the longest distance across the pore. In addition, we quantify the equivalent diameter, which is the diameter of a circle with the same area as the pore. The average pore size increases with decreasing weight fraction of ALP-containing fragments: the mean Feret diameter of samples made of 50 wt% ALP-containing fragments is $174 \pm 169 \mu\text{m}$, whereas that of samples made of 33 wt% ALP-containing fragments

is $195 \pm 167 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in **Figure 3d**. The mean equivalent diameter of samples containing 50 wt% ALP-loaded fragments is $156 \pm 151 \mu\text{m}$, which falls within the error range of the mean value for samples containing 33 wt% ALP-loaded enzymes, which is $145 \pm 138 \mu\text{m}$, indicating no significant difference in pore sizes between the two samples, as shown in **Figure S3**. We attribute the discrepancy between the two measured diameters to the elongated and irregular morphology of the polydisperse pores. By contrast, the size of pores in samples mineralized from 67% ALP-containing fragments is much smaller, with Feret diameters on the order of tens of microns or less, approaching the resolution limit of the CT scans.

If minerals form a percolating network, they strongly increase the stiffness and toughness of the composite.^[55-57] Our scaffolds can bear some load already after 1 day of mineralization, suggesting that minerals form a percolating network already after this short incubation time. All tested dried pillars can support a 500 g weight, which corresponds to at least 10,000 times their weight, after one day of mineralization, as qualitatively shown in **Figure S4**. These results hint at the potential of this material to bear load already within the first day of an intervention, in stark contrast to natural bone. To quantify the influence of the mineral content and porosity on the mechanical properties of the composites, we perform compression tests on samples that have been mineralized for 7 days. Control samples made of 100 wt% enzyme-containing fragments are elastic up to a strain of 3% whereafter they irreversibly break, as indicated by the slowly decreasing stress with increasing strain shown in **Figure 4a**. These samples are rather stiff with a compression modulus of 30 MPa. Samples made from scaffolds containing 67 wt% ALP-loaded enzymes have a similar compression modulus of 28 MPa and start to break at a strain of 6%. This behavior is similar to that reported for hollow thin-walled ceramics.^[58] By contrast, samples encompassing at most 50 wt% ALP-loaded fragments are softer and more extensible: Samples made from scaffolds containing 50 wt% ALP-loaded enzymes exhibit a compression modulus of 20 MPa, whereas those containing 33 wt% ALP-loaded enzymes have a compression modulus of 8 MPa, as shown in **Figure S5a**. Yet, the softest samples we tested have the highest yield stress: 3.7 MPa. The yield stress decreases to 1.8 MPa for samples made from 50 wt% ALP-loaded fragments and to 1.4 and 1.2 MPa for samples made from scaffolds with 67 wt% and 100 wt% ALP-loaded fragments, as shown in **Figure S5b**. These results hint at the importance of homogeneous mineralization for the toughness of these samples.

Figure 4. Mechanical properties of mineralized scaffolds. a) Overview of compression curves of HA-based composites after 7 days of mineralization as a function of the wt% of ALP-containing enzymes within the scaffold. (b-c) Specific b) modulus and c) strength of HA-based composites as a function of the wt% of ALP-loaded fragments present in the scaffolds. d) Asbhy plot of the compressive strength as a function of porosity of HA-based ceramics formed from scaffolds containing 33 wt% (pink) and 50 wt% (purple) ALP-loaded fragments and HA-based ceramics obtained from HA particles (gray squares)^[12], (red squares)^[13], (light green square)^[59], (dark green squares)^[18], (yellow circle)^[14], (orange circle)^[15], and nano HA with various organic templates (blue empty square)^[60], (light blue empty square)^[61], (light brown empty square)^[62], (dark brown empty square)^[23]. Empty symbols indicate HA-based ceramics that are not sintered; circles indicate HA-based ceramics that are 3D printable. Abbreviations: chitosan (CS), methylcellulose (MC), nanoHA (nHA), synthetic polymer (SP), Gelatin (Gel), Alginate (Alg), HA particles (pHA).

The stiffness of minerals typically decreases with increasing porosity. To assess if the measured reduction in compression modulus with decreasing wt% of ALP-loaded fragments present in the initial scaffolds is solely caused by the increased porosity of these samples, we quantify their densities and use them to normalize the compressive moduli. Samples that have been made from scaffolds with no more than 50 wt% ALP-loaded fragments exhibit an apparent density of $0.7 \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$, as shown in **Figure S6**. This value is significantly lower than that of hydroxyapatite, which is $3.16 \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$.^[63] The density of samples made from 67 wt%

ALP-containing enzymes is $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, whereas that of the control sample is $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, as shown in **Figure S6**. Using these densities, we obtain specific compression moduli that increase from $11 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^3$ for samples containing 33 wt% ALP-containing fragments to $28 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^3$ for samples made from 50 wt% ALP-containing fragments to 31 and $35 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^3$ for samples made from 67 wt% and 100 wt% ALP-containing samples, as shown in **Figure 4b**. We assign the highest specific compressive modulus of control samples to their dense shell.

The heterogeneous mineralization of control samples imparts them a high specific compressive modulus. However, it compromises the compressive strength. Indeed, the specific compressive strength increases from $1.2 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^3$ for samples made exclusively from ALP-containing fragments to $5.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^3$ for samples initially containing 33 wt% ALP-loaded fragments, as shown in **Figure 4c**. These values are similar to those of trabecular bone.^[64–66] The increase in specific compressive strength with decreasing concentration of ALP-loaded fragments in the initial scaffolds is assigned to the increasingly homogeneous mineral distribution, which results in a more even stress distribution. The more homogeneously distributed organic scaffold present within these composites efficiently dissipates energy, thereby further increasing the compressive strength.^[23,67,68]

Porous hydroxyapatite scaffolds typically have rather limited specific strength. Indeed, the hydroxyapatite scaffolds possessing a similar porosity to the composites introduced here typically have an inferior compressive strength, as summarized in the Ashby plot in **Figure 4d**. This comparison is particularly appealing because our scaffolds have been energy efficiently processed at room temperature, in stark contrast to most other reported scaffolds that were sintered.^[13,15,23] Note that hydroxyapatite-based porous scaffolds with higher specific compression strengths have been reported.^[12,14] However, these scaffolds were sintered, such that their processing is energy-consuming and limited to simple shapes.

An attractive method to process a wide variety of materials, including minerals, into complex 3D shapes with locally varying compositions is direct ink writing (DIW). Direct ink writing imparts stringent rheological requirements on its inks. To fulfill these rheological requirements, ceramic precursors are frequently formulated as polymer-based inks that are loaded with mineral fillers used as rheomodifiers. However, these formulations typically have to compromise flow stability and solid particle loading, resulting in materials possessing low mineral contents.^[69] Jammed microgels inherently fulfill the rheological requirements DIW imparts on its inks, such that our granular hydrogels can be 3D printed without any rheomodifiers. Indeed, our gelatin-based fragments are shear-thinning, as shown in **Figure S7a**, have a low strain at the yield point, where the storage modulus G' is equal to the loss modulus G'' , as shown in **Figure S7b**, and a fast stress recovery, as shown in **Figure S7c**. Hence, these inks can be direct ink written with commercial bioprinters.^[70–72] As a result of the

favorable rheological properties, this granular ink can be printed into cm-sized cylinders with low and high aspect ratios in air without any sacrificial bath, as exemplified in **Figure 5a**. The printed structures are incubated in a buffered aqueous solution containing calcium glycerophosphate for 7 days until fully mineralized (**Figure 5b i-ii**). The good shape retention of the ink allows printing more complex structures, such as a *Helicoprion* shark tooth, as shown in **Figure 5c i-ii**.

To assess the shape fidelity of the mineralized structures, we quantify the volume of scaffolds before and after having been mineralized for 1 and 7 days. After 1 day of mineralization, the volume of scaffolds containing 33 wt% ALP-loaded fragments decreases by 66%, limiting the shape fidelity of these structures in the early stages of mineralization. The volume of formulations containing 50 wt% ALP-loaded fragments decreases by 55% whereas that of control samples decreases by only 39% upon drying, as shown in **Figure 5d**. The volumetric shrinkage of samples is much lower after they have been mineralized for 7 days: Controls shrink by only 14% whereas samples formed from scaffolds containing 33 wt% ALP-loaded fragments shrink by 37% upon drying, as summarized in **Figure 5d**. We attribute the lower degree of shrinkage of controls and samples made from 67 wt% ALP-loaded fragments to their dense mineral shell.

To showcase the potential of our ink, we print a core composed of 33 wt% ALP-containing fragments, surrounded by a denser shell entirely made from ALP-containing fragments. To demonstrate the favorable rheological properties of both inks, we print and mineralize the shell and subsequently back-fill the core and vice-versa, as shown in **Figure 5e-f**. The same approach can be used to produce thin core-shell disks, as shown in **Figure S8**. This combination of high compressive modulus, high porosity, energy-efficient processing, 3D printability, and biocompatibility could thus far not be achieved, as summarized in the spider plot in **Figure 6**.

Figure 5. 3D printing of scaffolds. a) Enzyme-containing fragments are printed into a high aspect-ratio cylinder at room temperature in air b) before being mineralized for 7 days (i-ii). c) 3D printed *Helicoprion* shark tooth (i). The close-up ii) shows the level of details that is maintained after mineralization. The scale bars are 1 mm. d) Volumetric shrinkage upon drying of scaffolds as a function of the wt% of ALP-loaded fragments they have been made from. The empty circles refer to a mineralization time of day 1, the full ones to 7 days. Samples with heterogeneous mineralizations are marked with an asterisks. e) Photograph of 100 wt% ALP-containing fragments printed into cylinders before being mineralized for 7 days. After full mineralization the second ink comprising 33 wt% ALP-containing fragments is extruded to form the shell (i) and mineralized for 7 days (ii). f) The same approach is inverted printing first the 33 wt% ALP-containing fragment core and then the 100 wt% ALP-containing fragment shell (i) that is mineralized for 7 days (ii). The shell is partially damaged during drying due to differences in shrinkage.

Figure 6. Spider plot of HA-based porous ceramics showing their compressive strength, porosity, processing temperature and printability. HA-based ceramics are obtained from HA particles processed without binders (dark green)^[18] and with different binders: polyacrylamide (PAAm) (gray)^[12] and (yellow)^[14], gelatin (red)^[13], methylcellulose (MC) (light green)^[59], polyvinylalcohol (PVA) (orange)^[15], curdlan (blue)^[60], chitosan (CS) (light blue).^[61] This work is represented in pink. The axes scales represent the limits of the dataset: compressive strength from 0 to 17 MPa, porosity from 40 to 90 %, processing temperature from 1350 °C to 23 °C, and printability from 0 (not printable) to 1 (printable).

Our samples are exclusively made of naturally derived components such that we anticipated them to be biocompatible. To test our expectation, we assess MG-63 cell viability and morphology on samples that have been produced from scaffolds containing different fractions of enzyme-containing fragments. Live/Dead staining reveals that cells remain largely viable (green), with only a few dead cells (red) observed after 1 day, independent of the tested substrate, as shown in **Figure 7a**. After 7 days, an increase in live cells is evident, especially in scaffolds encompassing 33 wt% and 50 wt% enzyme-containing fragments, suggesting enhanced cell proliferation and survival over time, as shown in **Figure 7b**. Note that the viability of cells seeded on substrates produced from 100 wt% enzyme-containing fragments does not increase after 7 days, as shown in **Figure 7b**.

Samples made from substrates with no more than 50 wt% enzyme-containing fragments contain pores such that we expect cells to infiltrate them. To test our expectation, we analyze the spatial distribution of MG-63 cells by depth color-coding of confocal images acquired on Day 7 (**Figure 7a**, right column) and by quantifying the cumulative fluorescence intensity as a function of depth (**Figure 7c**). The depth-coded images reveal that cells predominantly remain at the surface of scaffolds made from at least 67 wt% enzyme-containing fragments. By

contrast, cells readily infiltrate scaffolds containing no more than 50 wt% enzyme-containing fragments, as shown in **Figure 7a iv, viii**. For example, in scaffolds encompassing 50 wt% enzyme-containing fragments, the cumulative fluorescence intensity of cells measured at a depth of 152 μm , reaches 0.79 ± 0.16 . The cumulative intensity measured at a depth of 152 μm is only slightly higher 0.87 ± 0.03 if scaffolds encompass 33 wt% enzyme-containing fragments. These values are very close to the ideal distribution line (0.76). By contrast, scaffolds containing higher enzyme-contents display much higher cumulative values: 0.9 ± 0.01 if scaffolds contain 67 wt% enzyme-loaded fragments and 0.97 ± 0.02 if scaffolds are exclusively composed of enzyme-containing fragments. These results suggest that homogeneously mineralized scaffolds that contain connected pores support initial cell infiltration, adhesion, spreading and subsequent proliferation, rendering them promising materials for tissue engineering.

Figure 7. Cell viability, morphology, and depth distribution of MG-63 cells seeded on top of HA based scaffolds obtained from enzyme-containing fragments with varying enzyme content. a) Live/Dead staining (green: live cells; red: dead cells) of seeded MG-63 cells after 1 and 7

days of culture in scaffolds encompassing 33 wt% (pink, i–iv), 50 wt% (purple, v–viii), 67 wt% (beige, ix–xii), and 100 wt% (grey, xiii–xvi) ALP containing fragments. Scale bars = 100 μm . Corresponding SEM images on Day 1 show the scaffold surface and adhered cells (white arrows indicate cells). Scale bars = 20 μm . Depth color-coded images (ImageJ plugin Stack Depth Color Code 0.0.2) on Day 7 reveal spatial distribution of cells within the scaffold. Scale bars = 100 μm . b) Quantification of cell viability (%) on Day 1 and Day 7 for each composition ($n = 3$), analyzed by two-way ANOVA with significance indicated between time points. Statistical significance: $p < 0.01$ (**) and $p < 0.001$ (***). c) Cumulative fluorescence intensity versus depth on Day 7, showing deeper infiltration in scaffolds with lower enzyme content.

Conclusions

We introduce an ALP-containing granular ink that can be 3D printed at room temperature and air into cm-sized structures, which are mineralized post-printing for 7 days to result in hydroxyapatite-based porous composites encompassing up to 68 wt% mineral. The porosity of the composites can be increased up to 52 vol% by tuning the ratio of enzyme-containing to enzyme-free fragments. Mineralized scaffolds can bear significant load already after 1 day of mineralization. Once fully mineralized, they reach compressive strength up to 3.7 MPa, corresponding to a specific compressive strength of $5.5 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^3$ without any sintering or thermal treatment. Our formulation is exclusively composed of naturally sourced precursors, supports high cell viability, spreading, and infiltration and has the potential to be used for *in vivo* applications. We foresee the combination of favorable compressive strength, porosity, biocompatibility, and energy-efficient and benign processability to open up new possibilities in the regeneration of broken bones that enables a fast loading of broken structures.

Data Availability

The raw and processed data required to reproduce these findings are available to download from Zenodo.

Authorship Contribution Statement

Francesca Bono Visualization, Validation, Data curation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. Project Administration. Writing – original draft. Writing – review & editing,

Anna Puiggali-Jou Data curation, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. Writing – review & editing.

Greta Cocchi Investigation, Data curation. Writing – review & editing.

Mariangela Miccoli Investigation, Data curation. Writing – review & editing

Marcy Zenobi-Wong Resources, Supervision, Project administration. Writing – review & editing.

Esther Amstad Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Materials and Methods

Materials. Gelatin from porcine skin (gelatin Type-A from porcine skin (gel strength 300, Sigma-Aldrich, G2500), urea (Sigma-Aldrich, 51456), phosphatase, Alkaline from bovine intestinal mucosa (ALP), >10 DEA units/mg (Sigma-Aldrich, P7640), alginic acid sodium salt from brown algae (Sigma-Aldrich, A1112), phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Gibco), calcium chloride (Carl Roth, CN93.1), calcium glycerophosphate hydrate (CaGP) (ThermoFisher, 10236322), triethanolamine (TEA) (Sigma-Aldrich, SDBB1174), glutaraldehyde (GA) (25 wt% in water, Sigma-Aldrich, G6257), hydrochloric acid (HCl) (Sigma-Aldrich, 84426), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (Carl Roth, 9356.1). MG-63 cells (osteosarcoma cell line, ATCC #CRL-1427; ATCC, Wesel, Germany), fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Gibco), Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) (Gibco), fibroblast growth factor 2 (FGF-2, PeproTech), Propidium Iodide (PI) (Fluka).

Buffer and incubation solution preparation. 0.2 M TEA buffer was prepared by dissolving TEA in water and adjusting the pH to 9.5 with 4 M HCl. The incubation solution was prepared by gradually dissolving CaGP in TEA buffer under vigorous stirring, yielding a final concentration of 0.1 M.

Glutaraldehyde solution preparation. The GA solution was prepared following a previously reported protocol.^[30] Briefly, 10 ml of a commercially available 25 wt% glutaraldehyde aqueous solution (corresponding to 2.65 M) were mixed with 0.6 mL 1 M NaOH to adjust the pH to 10.5. After 30 minutes, the mixture was neutralized by adding 0.15 mL 4 M HCl. To obtain 10 mL of the final 0.22 M solution, 0.848 mL of the pH-adjusted GA solution was diluted with 9.152 mL of TEA buffer.

Microfragments preparation. Microfragments were prepared by cryomilling bulk gelatin. A solution was obtained by dissolving 25 wt% gelatin at 40 °C in water. 10 mg of ALP enzyme per g of gelatin solution was dissolved in a mixture of GA solution (50 µL per mg ALP) and TEA buffer (25 µL per mg ALP), prepared as previously described, to covalently attach the enzyme. The enzyme solution was then poured into a beaker containing the gelatin solution (T = 40°C) and stirred vigorously. The solution was poured into a glass mold and cooled to room temperature to solidify the gelatin. The obtained bulk gel containing the encapsulated enzyme was stored at 4°C. The bulk gels were fragmented with an oscillatory cryomill (Cryomill, Retsch) using 1 stainless steel ball (d = 25 mm). The cryomilling protocol was as follows: 3 min of precooling at 5 Hz; 1 milling cycle of 1 min at 30 Hz. The prepared fragments were freeze-dried and stored at 4°C.

Ink preparation. Dry enzyme-loaded microfragments were resuspended in a 4 wt% alginate solution in PBS with a 1:4 volume ratio of dry fragments: alginate solution for 1 hour at 4 °C. To remove the supernatant, the suspension was centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3700 rpm and 7 °C (Mega Star 1.6R, VWR). The obtained ink was stored at 4 °C and used for 3D printing and casting.

Ink biomineralization. Once 3D printed or cast into the final shape, the ink was gelled by exposing it dropwise to a large excess of 1 M CaCl₂ solution. After 30 minutes, the ink was transferred into the incubation aqueous solution containing 0.1 M calcium glycerophosphate dissolved in TEA solution (0.2 M, pH 9.5). The solution was exchanged every 24 h for seven days. After the seventh day, samples were removed from the incubation solution, soaked in water for 25 minutes, and dried in a vacuum chamber at room temperature overnight before any measurement.

XRD measurements. The regular theta-theta scans for all samples were performed on a Panalytical Empyrean X-Ray polycrystalline diffractometer in Bragg-Brentano geometry, equipped with a long-focused seal Cu X-Ray tube ($\lambda_{K\alpha} = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$), and PIXcel 1D X-Ray detector. The patterns were collected in continuous mode between 5 and 60 degrees (2θ), with the step size of 0.02626 degrees. The baseline removal and peak search were performed with the Peak Analyzer tool in OriginPro2021.

Micro computed tomography. X-Ray μ CT was performed on an Ultratom micro tomography system (RX-SOLUTIONS). The dry samples were scanned at a voxel resolution of 1.05 mm, with a voltage of 45 kV and a current of 166 mA. Amira-Avizo v.2019.4 software was used for reconstruction, segmentation, and visualization. Image J was used for thresholding and calculations of the mineral, pore, and gel fractions. All the results in **Figure S2** are reported as mean \pm SD of all the obtained slices for each sample. All the measurements were performed on samples obtained by casting in a 4 mm x 2 mm mould.

Pore size distribution. The pore sizes were quantified from μ CT scans. For each sample, 15 scans equally distributed in the volume were used to obtain the size distribution. ImageJ was used for thresholding the pore area, excluding the gelatin, and Feret diameter calculations. The equivalent diameter is obtained from the area assuming circular pores. To ensure measurement reliability, pores with Feret diameters below 45 μ m (the resolution threshold is \sim 3 μ m, voxel size) were excluded from analysis, as they were not consistently visible in the raw micro-CT images and likely represent artifacts due to noise and over-segmentation. To compare the size distributions a two-sample *t*-test assuming equal

variances was used. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$. All tests were performed in OriginPro.

Volume shrinkage and density measurements. The volume shrinkage percentage (V_s) was calculated as follows:

$$V_s = \frac{V_i - V_f}{V_i} \times 100$$

Where V_i is the initial volume calculated by measuring diameter, thickness and mass of 3 distinct cylinders as prepared in a 6 mm x 2 mm mold, after removing the excess water from the surface, and V_f is the final volume of the same set of 3 samples measured in the same way after overnight drying in a vacuum chamber.

Fragment rheological characterization. Rheological measurements were performed on a DHR-3 TA Instrument rheometer with an 8 mm diameter parallel plate steel geometry. All measurements were performed at 25°C, with a 1000 μm gap and repeated on 3 distinct samples of enzyme-free and enzyme-containing fragments suspended in PBS containing 4 wt% alginate that have been jammed by 10 minutes centrifugation at 3700 rpm and 7 °C (Mega Star 1.6R, VWR). Amplitude sweeps were performed at 10 $\text{rad}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ for a strain range of 0.01 to 200%. Frequency sweeps were performed within the linear viscoelastic regime at a strain value of 0.2 % in a frequency range of 0.1-25 Hz. Shear recovery measurements were performed at 10 rad/s alternating 200 s at 0.2% with 200 s at 100% strain.

All the represented data were obtained from three independent samples and are reported as mean \pm SD.

Size distribution. Optical microscopy images were obtained with a Nikon Eclipse TS100 microscope. The equivalent diameters of the microfragments were calculated as the average of the two diagonals measured with Image J.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Mineralized samples were finely ground in a mortar before testing with TGA (TGA 4000, PerkinElmer). The measurements were performed from 30 °C to 850 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} with an air flow rate of 20 mL min^{-1} , and holding at 850 °C for 10 minutes before cooling down. Gelatin content was estimated from mass loss between 200–500 °C. Pure gelatin left a 6 wt% residue at 850 °C, which was used to calculate its char contribution that was subtracted from the final residue at 850 °C to determine the HA content. The represented data were obtained from at least three independent samples and are reported as mean \pm SD. The full curves used for the calculations are reported in **Figure S9**.

Compression measurements. Compression tests were performed on cylindrical samples obtained by casting the ink in 6 mm diameter and 6 mm tall molds. After incubation, all the samples were rinsed with water for 20 minutes and dried in a vacuum chamber overnight before testing with a commercial machine (ZwickiLine, 5 kN load cell, Zwick Roell), compressed at a constant velocity of 5 mm/min until 40% strain was reached. The compression modulus was calculated as the slope of the initial linear region, from 0.7% to 1.5% strain. The compression strength was obtained from the maximum load in the curve before 15% of deformation. All the curves are reported in **Figure S10**. All the reported results were obtained from at least three independent samples and are reported as mean \pm SD.

3D printing. Jammed gelatin-alginate microfragments containing ALP were loaded in a 3 mL Luer lock syringe. The syringe was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 1 minute to remove trapped air bubbles at 7 °C. 3D printing was carried out with a commercial 3D bioprinter (BIO X, Cellink) at 12 mm/s and 60 kPa or 70 kPa. The printing bed was maintained at 20 °C. The granular ink was extruded through a blunt needle (20G, DT = 603 μ m) using a pressure-driven piston.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). TEM experiments were performed on a Talos F200S Thermo Fisher Scientific microscope (200 kV with a 5 nA beam current). Bright-field (BF) TEM images were acquired with a Ceta CMOS camera and with a 20 μ m-diameter contrast aperture. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) was acquired with a 10 μ m-diameter selected area aperture at a 520 mm camera length. Energy dispersive X-ray spectrum was averaged over an entire nanoparticle, the C-line originates from the thin film supporting the nanoparticles, and the Cu K-lines at 8 keV are an extra (stray radiation) signal from the support grid that originates from the nanoparticle sample. For diffraction analysis, spatial frequencies were calibrated using a known 5 nm⁻¹ scale bar. Radial line profiles were extracted using ImageJ, and interplanar spacings d were calculated using the following relation:

$$d [\text{\AA}] = \frac{10}{s[\text{nm}^{-1}]}$$

Cell expansion and seeding. MG-63 cells (osteosarcoma cell line, ATCC #CRL-1427; ATCC, Wesel, Germany) were expanded in a proliferation medium composed of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) enriched with 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 μ g/mL gentamicin (Gibco), and 5 ng/mL fibroblast growth factor 2 (FGF-2). The cells were kept at 37 °C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂ and passaged when reaching approximately 80% confluency. For seeding, cells were detached with trypsin, resuspended in DMEM containing 10% (v/v) FBS and 10 μ g/mL gentamicin, and centrifuged for 5 minutes at 500 \times g. After

counting, 100,000 cells were seeded onto each composite construct (prepared in a 4 mm × 2 mm mold) and maintained in culture for either 1 or 7 days.

Live/Dead imaging. For viability assessment, samples were incubated for 40 minutes in DMEM (without FBS) supplemented with 1:1000 Calcein AM (Invitrogen) and 1:500 Propidium Iodide (PI). Subsequently, they were washed three times with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Imaging was carried out using a Leica SP8 microscope equipped with a 10× dry objective. Z-stacks were collected from the sample surface at 4 μm intervals, reaching a depth of 200 μm. The final images shown in this work were produced as maximum intensity z-projections.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). At the end of the culture period, cell-seeded samples were rinsed with PBS and fixed for 1 hour in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). Dehydration was performed through a graded ethanol series (from 20% up to 95%), followed by air drying under a fume hood. The dried samples were then coated with a 10 nm carbon layer using a CCU-010 Carbon Coater (Safematic). SEM analysis was conducted with a Zeiss Merlin microscope operated at 2 kV.

Cell infiltration. Cell depth distribution within the scaffolds was analyzed using the green fluorescence channel (live cells) from the Live/Dead staining. Confocal z-stacks were processed in ImageJ/Fiji using the Stack Depth Color Code plugin (v0.0.2), which assigns pseudo-colors according to the relative depth of each optical slice. For quantitative analysis, the cumulative fluorescence intensity was calculated along the z-axis. Briefly, the integrated intensity of each slice in the green channel was measured, normalized to the total fluorescence intensity of the entire stack, and plotted as a cumulative sum as a function of depth. To account for biological variability, three independent replicates per condition were analyzed. The resulting cumulative intensity profiles were compared to an ideal uniform distribution line, representing a theoretical linear increase of intensity with depth.

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